

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Trends in Food Science & Technology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/tifs

Navigating the old and the new of anti-nutritional factors: A comprehensive and critical exploration of sustainable protein-rich ingredients and innovative processing techniques

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Anti-nutrients
Food processing
Microalgae
Single-cell proteins
Pulses
Rapeseed
Insect

ABSTRACT

Background: Anti-nutritional factors (ANFs) are a key consideration in the development of novel, sustainable, protein-rich ingredients, as their levels are influenced by both ingredient selection and food processing techniques.

Scope and approach: This review, part of the Giant Leaps Horizon Europe-co-funded project, examines the chemical characterization, biological effects, and mechanisms of action of ANFs in a diverse range of alternative protein sources, including legumes, insects, algae, and microbial biomass. This study assesses how traditional and innovative food processing methods, such as fermentation, germination, enzymes, extrusion, affect ANF activity and the nutritional quality of alternative ingredients.

Key findings and conclusions: Innovative processing can mitigate the adverse effects of ANFs while preserving or even enhancing the health-promoting properties of foods. However, limitations and inconsistencies in current analytical methods for quantifying ANFs can lead to a misrepresentation of their levels, activity, processing stability, and bioactivity, thereby impacting the nutritional quality of ingredients. Furthermore, the interactions between ANFs and the gut microbiota are considered, particularly on the production of bioactive compounds like short-chain fatty acids. In conclusion, this review underscores the critical need for further research into ANF dynamics and the development of improved analytical methods. Accurate data on ANF levels are crucial for effective safety assessments and for ensuring that alternative protein ingredients are not nutritionally inferior. Ultimately, consumer trust in the safety and nutrition of novel foods is essential for their market acceptance and for advancing the transition towards sustainable food systems that address global environmental issues.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2025.105365>

Received 25 March 2025; Received in revised form 2 October 2025; Accepted 4 October 2025

Available online 8 October 2025

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1. Introduction

The European Green Deal promotes sustainable food systems by aiming to reduce the environmental impact of traditional animal agriculture impact. A key component, the Farm to Fork Strategy, targets “net zero” emissions, partly by encouraging a shift towards alternative proteins. This transition is supported by growing consumer interest in plant-based proteins, such as those from lentils, chickpeas, and peas, driven by environmental, health, and ethical concerns (Etter et al., 2024). Adopting a so called “flexitarian diet”, defined as reducing animal protein intake by 25 % in favour of plant-based alternatives, could lower greenhouse gas emissions by 40 % and water use by 10 % (Mariotti & Gardner, 2019). The adoption of flexitarian diets in Europe varies geographically and demographically, with rates ranging from 5 % to 26 % of the population. For instance, Greece shows the highest proportion of individuals following this dietary pattern, whereas Eastern Europe lags. Young adults are the demographic most likely to adopt this lifestyle (Kamin et al., 2024; Portugal-Nunes et al., 2023; Statista Search Department, 2024a, 2024b).

Shifting from highly digestible animal proteins to alternatives necessitates that the latter possess at least an equivalent nutritional quality. Globular seed storage proteins from plants (e.g., 7S and 11S globulins) are inherently less digestible than animal proteins (e.g., casein), primarily because their rigid structures conceal cleavage sites from digestive enzymes. Furthermore, the presence of ANFs in both plant and non-plant alternative protein sources can further decrease their digestibility.

ANFs, which vary in structure and molecular weight, are naturally produced by organism as a defence mechanism against biotic and abiotic stresses and pest. They are classified as non-proteinaceous (np-ANFs) and proteinaceous (p-ANFs) types and can negatively affect the health and growth of organisms that ingest them. They may act as toxins, interfering with nutrient digestion, absorption and metabolism in the gastrointestinal tract, or exert adverse metabolic effects in other tissues. Their concentration in ingredients and food products depends on environmental conditions, downstream treatments, and processing methods, like milling and fractionation (Salim et al., 2023). Notably, ANF levels may increase with rising global temperatures due to climate change (Kashyap et al., 2024). Their presence in alternative protein ingredients can also exacerbate nutritional deficiencies among the vulnerable populations, such as infants, children, and older adults, who have undeveloped or impaired gastrointestinal systems (Moughan et al., 2024).

The activity of ANFs, such as trypsin inhibitors, phytates, tannins, oxalates, and glucosinolates, can be modulated throughout traditional methods like soaking or bio-processes, such as fermentation and germination. These processed are commonly used in home cooking and industrial food preparation, for example in canning legumes. Fermented and germinated ingredients have traditionally been used to produce foods like sauerkraut or malt for beer. Similarly, the preparation of legumes sprouts and fermented vegetables like kimchi, practice long established in Asia, are gaining popularity in Europe. Technological processes, including ingredients fractionation for protein isolate and concentrate production, heat treatment, debittering, and extrusion, can also influence the abundance and activity of ANFs in commercial ingredients and food products (Patterson et al., 2017).

In many parts of the world, including Canada, UK and the European Union, numerous alternative protein ingredients are considered novel. Consequently, a general safety assessment is required before these foods can be placed on the market. This assessment includes an evaluation of their nutritional quality. Information on the levels and activity of ANFs in a novel ingredient forms an integral part of the data package required for this nutritional assessment. Although ANFs in plants are well-documented, these compounds can also be present in novel ingredients produced from other types of organism and may become concentrated in fractionated ingredients. Therefore, it is crucial to understand how existing knowledge of plant-based ANFs can be applied to

novel foods entering the market, such as algae, insects, and microbial biomass, as substitutes for animal proteins. New types of ANFs, unique to these sources, may also require evaluation.

As part of the co-funded Giant Leaps Horizon Europe project, this review compares the role of ANFs in affecting the nutritional quality of conventional ingredients, such as alternative pulses, cereals and protein fractions, and innovative sources like unicellular organisms (e.g., microalgae, microbial biomasses), rapeseed meal, and insects is compared. The ingredients were strategically selected to represent a broad spectrum of alternative protein sources, ranging from well-established options like pulses to emerging ones such as microbial biomasses, microalgae, and insects. This selection allows the review to address varying levels of scientific understanding, technological maturity, and regulatory readiness. Furthermore, *in silico* bioinformatic analyses are being conducted to examine the expression of p-ANFs in emerging ingredients and the metabolic pathways leading to np-ANF formation. The review also includes a critical evaluation of existing analytical methods for determining ANFs. The goal is to identify gaps that could compromise their accurate assessment and to guide future research toward more reliable techniques. Finally, the review explores the interactions between ANFs and gut microbiota in shedding light on potential health implications.

2. Global perspectives on novel food regulation

Many countries and regions worldwide, including the European Union (EU) member states, the UK, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, have regulations requiring that a safety assessment be conducted before a novel food can be placed on the market. This risk assessment is conducted by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) in the EU and the Food Standards Agency (FSA) in the UK. In Canada, the assessment is undertaken by Health Canada, while Food Standards Australia New Zealand (FSANZ) performs this role for both Australia and New Zealand. All jurisdictions provide guidance and adhere to the principals of risk assessment laid out by the CODEX Alimentarius Commission with modifications relevant to the populations whose health they are designed to protect (Brooke-Taylor & Grinter, 2023; Crevel, 2023; Taylor & Godefroy, 2023). When a whole genome sequence is available for microorganisms, a bioinformatic analysis for ANFs is also performed. Because these risk assessments focus on specific ingredients, they consider the impact of the manufacturing process on the resulting levels and activities of ANFs. Other jurisdictions may take different approaches, notably the USA, which follows a self-regulatory model. In this system, manufacturers must conduct their own safety assessment to establish a consensus among qualified experts that the substance is safe under its condition of use. Manufacturers have the option to notify the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) that an ingredient has been given “Generally Recognized as Safe” (GRAS) status. The FDA then responds either with no comments regarding the notifier’s GRAS status determination or by concluding that the notice provides an insufficient basis for such a determination.

3. Chemical characterization, mechanism of action and analysis of ANFs

Integrating bioinformatics with genetic, metabolomic, and proteomic analyses serves as an initial screening method to guide *in vitro* assessments, and enhance the understanding of ANFs, particularly p-ANFs, in food ingredients. However, risk assessment frameworks require data on ANFs in ingredients be determined using validated detection and quantification methods, preferably performed by accredited laboratories. Existing analytical techniques are often unsuitable for this purpose, especially for novel foods. While previous work has addressed the detection of active molecules in raw ingredients (Purohit et al., 2023), the quantification of active ANFs post-production remains challenging due to insufficient extraction under physiological conditions. The

extraction of p-ANFs is especially complex, as they must retain their native structure to remain active. Protein solubility depends on factors such as primary structure, interactions within the food, and location within the matrix. Consequently, low extraction yields may underestimate the presence or potency of p-ANF. Structural barriers, such as exoskeletons of insect and the cell walls of microalgae, fungi, and plants, further hinder protein extraction. Although complex buffer systems aid exploratory proteomics analyses, they may also inactivate p-ANFs, rendering them unsuitable for physiological assessment. In contrast, np-ANFs do not require physiological buffers, which simplifies their quantification.

In this review, we examined current methods for quantifying both p- and np-ANFs as summarised in [Supplementary Tables 1 and 3](#). We evaluate existing techniques for identifying active ANFs in ingredients and foods, focusing on those relevant to dietary transitions, including lectins, enzyme inhibitors, and phytic acids. This review also highlights the limitations of these methods when applied to food processing, which can lead to significant data misinterpretation. We complement this analysis with data mining of protein and metabolic pathway databases. [Table 1](#) summarises the key findings for a set of analysed alternative protein ingredients from plants and exemplar insect, microalgal, and microbial species. While this table focuses on the whole source material, the main body of the review incorporates available information about its derived fractions. This distinction is crucial, as an ANF present in the whole source may be significantly enriched or lost during processing. The presence of these compounds in the whole sources and their fractions is discussed in [Section 3.1 and 3.2](#), while the effects of processing are reviewed in [Section 4](#).

3.1. Non-proteinaceous anti-nutritional factors (np-ANFs)

3.1.1. Saponins

Saponins are plant secondary metabolites found in cereals, legumes, green leaves, and some marine organisms. These amphiphilic molecules comprise a hydrophobic aglycone, typically a 30-carbon triterpenoid or steroid skeleton, and a hydrophilic glycone with one or more sugars ([Timilsena et al., 2023](#)). The aglycone structure determines the classification of saponins as triterpenoid or steroid saponins. The steroidal skeleton has five rings and 27 carbon atoms, forming either furostanol or spirostanol structure, while triterpenoid saponins have six rings and 30 carbon atoms ([Fig. 1](#)). Both types contain various functional groups ($-OH$, $-COOH$, $-CH_3$), which generate structural diversity influenced by both aglycone content and the sugar chain composition. The analysis of saponins from plant tissue has been comprehensively reviewed ([Supplementary Table 1](#)) ([Cheok et al., 2014](#)).

Due to their amphipathic nature, saponins can disrupt cell membranes, leading to haemolysis *in vitro*. However, large doses are required to cause local gut mucosal inflammation. They can also act as ANFs by forming insoluble complexes with proteins, lipids, minerals like iron, zinc and calcium, influencing negatively nutrient absorption ([Schreiner et al., 2022](#)).

The concentration of total saponins is notable in lentils (3.50 mg/g), faba beans (4.00 mg/g), oats (2.17 mg/g), and quinoa (24.20 mg/g) ([Ahuja et al., 2015](#); [Bhinder et al., 2021](#); [S. Kaur et al., 2019](#); [Sharma, 2021](#)). Interestingly, insect meals, from species such as cricket, contain approximately 53 mg/g of saponins. These compounds contribute to the insects' defence mechanisms, with levels varying based on rearing conditions and feed types ([Siddiqui et al., 2024](#)). Yeast and other fungi, species like *Pleurotus* (0.0016 mg/g) can also produce saponin-like compounds as secondary metabolites ([Effiong et al., 2024](#)), with the levels that can change depending on the fermentation condition. Saponins are also secondary metabolites of algae, where they contribute to ecological interactions and can be present up to 57.5 mg/g in *Chlorella* spp. ([Ridlo et al., 2023](#)).

3.1.2. Phytates

Phytic acid, also known as myoinositol (6)-hexakis (dihydrogen phosphate) or InsP6, is a compound that occurs naturally in plants, animals, and soil. It typically exists as phytate, forming salts with mono- and divalent cations such as potassium (K⁺), magnesium (Mg²⁺), and calcium (Ca²⁺) ([Salim et al., 2023](#)). With its six phosphate groups, myo-inositol hexaphosphate (InsP6) is the most potent form. Lower phosphorylated forms, such as InsP5 and InsP4, also contribute to chelation, although their effect diminishes with fewer phosphate groups. Consequently, the ion-chelating ability of these compounds is directly proportional to their degree of phosphorylation. This chelation of divalent cations leads to reduced bioavailability of essential minerals. Phytates can also affect the protein digestion by binding to proteins and digestive enzymes, hindering their break down into amino acids ([Nissar et al., 2017](#)) ([Fig. 2](#)). Phytate-protein interactions are pH-dependent; specifically, when the pH is below a protein's isoelectric point, the anionic phosphate groups of phytate bind strongly to the cationic groups of that protein.

Phytic acid is present in most legumes, with concentrations of approximately 13 mg/g in lentils and an average concentration of 32 mg/g in faba bean flour ([Adamidou et al., 2011](#)). The levels can vary depending on the cultivar, the environmental factors and ingredient processing. It is also found in oats (11 mg/g), and quinoa (4 mg/g) ([Bhinder et al., 2021](#); [Gołębiewska et al., 2022](#); [S. Kaur et al., 2019](#)). Low levels are also detected in microalgae and insects; for example, *Chlorella*

Table 1

ANFs in alternative protein sources. The table results from a literature review, implemented with p-ANFs with a review of the UNIPROT database to gather information about protein sequences.

	Vicia faba	Lens culinaris	Avena sativa	Chenopodium quinoa	Brassica napus	Chlorella sp	Xanthobacter sp	Acheta sp
PROTEIC ANTI-NUTRIENTS								
α-amylase inhibitors	–	–	x	–	–	–	–	–
Lectins	\$	\$	–	x	x	x	x,+	–
Serine protease inhibitors	\$	\$	x	x	x	x	–	–
Thiaminase	–	–	–	+	+	+	–	–
NON-DIGESTIBLE CARBOHYDRATES								
Chitin	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	■
Oligosaccharides	■	■	–	–	–	–	–	–
Polysaccharides	–	–	■	–	–	–	–	–
LOW MOLECULAR WEIGHT ANTI-NUTRIENTS								
Phytates	■	■	■	■	■	■	–	■
Phenolic compounds	■	■	■	■	■	■	–	■
Oxalates	–	–	–	■	–	–	–	■
Saponins	■	■	■	■	–	■	–	■
Toxic ANFs	■	–	–	–	–	■	–	■

Legend: \$ evidence at protein level, * evidence at transcript level, x inferred from homology, + protein predicted, ■ scientific literature available, - no knowledge available.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of representative non-proteinaceous anti-nutritional factors: (a) Phytic acid, (b) Gallic acid, (c) Vicine, (d) Linamarin, (e) N-acetyl-D-glucosamine – chitin monomer, (f) Progoitrin, (g) 3-Butenyl isothiocyanate, and (h) Solanine.

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of np-ANFs inhibiting a generic protein, with polyphenols (right) and phytate (left) interacting through key amino acids. The left panel of phytate shows the chelating action of bivalent cations.

spp. contains approximately 0.6 mg/g, while cricket meal contains between 0.001 up to 2.4 mg/g of phytates (Asaniyan & Ogundele, 2020; Siddiqui et al., 2024). As with other ANFs, the level of phytate in insects depends on their diet.

Several methods for phytic acid quantification exist, but they have notable limitations, as comprehensively reviewed by Kahruman et al. (2020). Although quantifying phytic acid with the Wade reagent (a ferric chloride and sulfosalicylic acid reactive) is rapid, this approach can be expensive and yields more variable results than other spectrophotometric methods, such as the Chen or Haug-Lantzsch methods. Additionally, the Wade method can be affected by the ingredient's protein content, as iron can form complexes with proteins that subsequently precipitate and interfere with the determination (Kahruman et al., 2020). The AOAC Official Method SM 986.11, based on Anion Exchange Chromatography (AEC), acid hydrolysis, and colorimetric phosphorus determination, is the widely accepted standard. This method separates phytic acid (InsP6), the most abundant myo-inositol phosphate in seeds (>90 %). However, minor forms of myo-inositol phosphates (i.e., InsP3, InsP4, InsP5), which can be present at high concentrations in processed samples, or those exposed to phytase, an enzyme found in animals, plants, and microorganisms, can co-elute with the InsP6-chelating form. This leads to an overestimation of the "active phytic acid", the forms with the highest capacity to chelate divalent ions (Baruah et al., 2017; McKie & McCleary, 2016). Consequently, the simple quantification of total myo-inositol phosphates can obscure the true chelating potential of an ingredient. An alternative method involves the use of an InsP_n-specific phytase following acidic extraction, which recognises phytic acid (InsP6) and the lower myo-inositol phosphate forms (i.e., InsP2, InsP3, InsP4, InsP5) (McKie and McCleary (2016). This method should improve the detection specificity of processed ingredients and foods. However, it shares a key assumption with the official AOAC method 986.11: It presumes that all released phosphorus originates exclusively from the InsP6 form. This assumption ignores potential contributions from other phosphate esters, such as the lesser-phosphorylated myo-inositol phosphates. Consequently, a critical assessment reveals that currently available methods for phytic acid determination are inadequate for validating deactivation processes, as they cannot reliably confirm the reduction of the most active, ion-chelating forms of phytate. Therefore, evaluating the true effectiveness of a deactivation method might require bioaccessibility assays. In these assays, the digestibility of the treated ingredient is compared to its untreated counterpart, and the key metric is the quantity of freely absorbable divalent ions (e.g., iron, zinc). This approach provides a direct measure of nutrient availability, rather than relying on the concentration of phytic acid itself.

Regarding naturally occurring phytase, its presence could potentially serve as an indirect indicator of phytic acid in an ingredient. Although the UniProt and NCBI protein databases do not annotate phytase in *Chlorella* or *Acheta*, microbial biomass like *Xanthobacter* does contain phytase-like proteins. However, this does not imply or roll out the presence of an InsP6-active form in the ingredient, which still needs to be assessed analytically.

3.1.3. Phenolic compounds

Although polyphenols and dietary fibres are essential components of the diet due to their antioxidant properties and positive effects on the gut microbiota, this review classifies them as ANFs. This classification is based on their potential to interact with proteins and digestive enzymes, thereby reducing protein digestibility and absorption, particularly in plant-based meat and dairy substitutes compared to their animal counterparts (Moughan, 2021).

Phenolic compounds, defined by one or more hydroxyl groups attached to an aromatic ring (Fig. 1), are broadly categorised into four groups: (i) phenolic acids, (ii) flavonoids, (iii) polyphenolic amides, and (iv) other polyphenols, such as resveratrol, ellagic acid derivatives, curcumin, and rosmarinic acid (Tsao, 2010).

Tannins, a water-soluble and astringent subgroup of polyphenols, are classified as either as hydrolysable or condensed. They interfere with the digestion by forming complexes with carbohydrates, proteins, and mineral ions which impedes efficient nutrient utilisation (Ojo, 2022). This interaction is driven by their ability to bind with specific amino acids residues. For instance, the astringent sensation from high-tannin foods like tea and coffee is caused by tannins binding to proline-Rich Proteins (PRPs) in saliva (Fig. 2)(Ozdal et al., 2013). Because these insoluble complexes precipitate in the mouth, their subsequent impact on nutrient absorption in the gastrointestinal track may be reduced or eliminated. Other binding mechanisms also contribute to the anti-nutritional effects of phenolics. Quinones, which are highly reactive, can form covalent bond with nucleophilic side chains of amino acids (e.g. lysine, cysteine, methionine), affecting both dietary proteins and digestive enzymes (Seczyk et al., 2019). Additionally, weaker hydrophobic interactions can occur between phenols and hydrophobic amino acids (Fig. 2). Despite these effects, tannins can also offer prebiotic benefits. Their ability to associate with dietary fibre makes them resistant to digestion, allowing them to reach the large intestine where they can serve as a substrate for gut microbes (Rana et al., 2022). Phenolic compounds, including phenolic acids and flavonoids and tannins and condensed tannins, are present in most emerging alternative proteins ingredients. They are found in legumes, cereals and rapeseeds as well as in microalgae, crickets and edible fungi (S. Kaur et al., 2019; Lin et al., 2022; J. Lu et al., 2024; Siddiqui et al., 2024). In faba beans and lentils, the predominant forms of phenolic acids are hydroxycinnamic compounds, while procyanidins (a type of condensed tannin) are the main flavonoids (Y. Lu et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2017). Catechins are present in both, though epicatechin and quercetin are especially abundant in faba beans (Y. Lu et al., 2018). Lentils also contain flavan-3-ols, dihydrochalcones, stilbenes, and gallates (Singh et al., 2017). Quinoa contains high levels of quercetin and kaempferol, which are ubiquitous in many fruits and vegetables (Pereira et al., 2020). Avenanthramides are a group of phenolic alkaloids found mainly in oats (Soycan et al., 2019). Rapeseed primarily contains sinapine, sinapic acid, and sinapoyl-glucosides (Zhang et al., 2022).

Tannins concentrations vary significantly across these sources. Reported levels include faba bean (13 mg/g), lentils (9 mg/g), oats (3 mg/g), quinoa (0.3 mg/g), the microalgae *Chlorella* spp. (3 mg/g), and rapeseed hulls (up to 0.02 mg/g) (Adamidou et al., 2011; Asaniyan & Ogundele, 2020; F. Chen et al., 2022; S. Kaur et al., 2019; Y. Li et al., 2024; Siddiqui et al., 2024). Insects, including crickets, also contain tannins, with cricket meals containing 0.06 mg/g (Asaniyan & Ogundele, 2020; Siddiqui et al., 2024).

3.1.4. Oxalates

Like phytates, oxalates are chelating agents that inhibit the absorption of minerals such as calcium, iron, and zinc by forming insoluble complexes. Oxalic acid is a dicarboxylic organic acid characterised by its low molecular weight, high acidity, and strong chelating and reducing abilities (Karamad et al., 2019). Oxalates are particularly abundant in quinoa (2.3 mg/g) and can be found in insects, with concentrations in cricket meals ranging from 0.1 up to 9 mg/g (Asaniyan & Ogundele, 2020; Siddiqui et al., 2024).

3.1.5. Glucosinolates and isothiocyanates

Glucosinolates (formerly known as thioglucosides) are sulphur-rich, anionic secondary metabolites. They are hydrolysed by the enzyme myrosinase into bioactive compounds, including isothiocyanates, nitriles, goitrin, and thiocyanates (Fig. 1) (Hanschen & Schreiner, 2017). Glucosinolates are classified into three main groups based on their amino acid precursors: aliphatic (derived from amino acids like alanine, leucine, isoleucine, valine, and methionine), indole (from tryptophan), and aromatic (from phenylalanine or tyrosine) (Bell et al., 2018; Ishida et al., 2014).

The taste and flavour of Brassicaceae vegetables are significantly

shaped by glucosinolates and their hydrolysis products, which can impact consumer palatability. Many intact glucosinolates, including sinigrin, gluconapin, and progoitrin, are associated with a bitter taste. The hydrolysis of progoitrin produces goitrin, which is noted for its extreme bitterness. In contrast, the characteristic pungent or "hot" sensation is caused by isothiocyanates. For instance, allyl isothiocyanate (derived from sinigrin) is responsible for the sharp taste of mustard and horseradish, while raphasatin (from dehydroerucin) contributes to the pungency of radish. However, not all these compounds impart strong flavours; glucoraphanin, for example, is considered having little perceptible taste (Bell et al., 2018). Among the hydrolysis products, thiocyanates are major goitrogens that compete with iodine for thyroid uptake, potentially causing goitre and hypothyroidism, especially with low iodine intake. Isothiocyanates, containing a N=C=S group, exhibit cytotoxic effects that can also disrupt thyroid function. Additionally, glucosinolates may reduce the availability of essential mineral, including copper and selenium (Akram et al., 2021).

Glucosinolates are widely present in Brassica species, such as cabbage, broccoli, rapeseed, mustard, Brussels sprouts, and horseradish. Their concentration in de-oiled rapeseed seeds can be as high as 150 mg/g, compared to 4.2 mg/g in commercial canola and rapeseed meals (Clarke, 2010; Gołębiewska et al., 2022; Prieto et al., 2019). The most abundant glucosinolates in rapeseed meal including progoitrin, gluconapin, glucobrassicinapin, glucoraphanin, sinigrin and gluconasturtiin (Xie et al., 2022). While a predicted pathway for glucosinolate formation in *Chlorella* is available in the Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) database (pathway: cvr00966), key enzymes for this pathway are absent or unannotated in currently available genomic sequences. Despite their potential negative effects, glucosinolates also offer health benefits, including anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. They may help reduce the risk of cancers, such as prostate cancer, by inhibiting cancer cell growth and reducing inflammation (Akram et al., 2021).

3.1.6. Non digestible carbohydrates

Non digestible carbohydrates (Fig. 1) can hinder the digestive enzymes by increasing the viscosity of the chyme and binding proteins through weak interaction (Moughan, 2021). The concentration of these non-digestible carbohydrates varies significantly across protein ingredients: flours typically contain significant amounts of fibre, protein concentrates have low fibre content, and isolates contain virtually none. In alternative novel ingredients, the composition of non-digestible carbohydrates is also diverse. For instance, crickets contain chitin (Kipkoeh, 2023), while the alga *Chlorella* contains a blend of cellulose, hemicellulose and pectin (Zanchetta et al., 2021). For ingredients derived from microbial biomass, these carbohydrates, encompassing both soluble and insoluble fibres, can constitute a substantial proportion of the final product. They range from plant cell walls and insect exoskeletons. Both plant-derived fibres and chitin are known to interact with the mucous layer covering the enterocytes (Collado-González et al., 2019; Meldrum et al., 2017). Polysaccharides like β -glucans are found in oats at an average of 16 mg/g (S. Kaur et al., 2019), while legume cell walls are rich in pectic polysaccharides and xyloglucans (Jarvis et al., 2003). Chitin and its deacetylated form, chitosan, are present in insects; crickets, for example, contain up to 49.8 mg/kg (fresh weight) and 137.2 mg/kg (dry weight) (Magara et al., 2021). These are complemented by α -galactosides, which are found in legumes such as lentils and include raffinose (0.42 mg/g), stachyose (1.87 mg/g) and verbasose (0.49 mg/g). Their levels can be almost tenfold higher in faba beans, with a concentration of 3.90 mg/g for raffinose, 13.70 mg/g of stachyose and 15.00 mg/g of verbasose (Mayer Labba et al., 2021; Wang & Daun, 2006). Since human enzymes cannot digest these compounds, they are fermented by gut bacteria in the colon, producing gases like methane and hydrogen that cause gastrointestinal discomfort. This is especially problematic for short-chain oligosaccharides known as FODMAPs (fermentable oligosaccharides, disaccharides,

monosaccharides, and polyols). When consumed in sufficient quantities by susceptible individuals, FODMAPs can cause gastrointestinal distress, leading some to adopt a low FODMAP diet (Algera et al., 2022).

3.2. Proteinaceous anti-nutritional factors (p-ANFs)

Understanding the mechanism of action of ANFs is key to assessing their impact on nutrient absorption. This section details the classification of ANFs based on their structure and function. Supplementary Table 2 outlines their structural features and inhibition activity, while Supplementary Table 3 summarises quantitative and accredited reference methods for their analysis.

3.2.1. Serine-protease inhibitors

Protease inhibitors (PIs) are proteins that prevent harmful protease activity during seed dormancy. While their role in plant stress tolerance is well-established, their involvement in other physiological processes remains less understood. In their active form, PIs can interfere with human digestive enzymes and impair macronutrient absorption (Kårlund et al., 2021). Plant seeds and tubers contain inhibitors of trypsin, chymotrypsin, carboxypeptidases, elastase, and other serine proteases. This inhibition can be reversible or irreversible; for instance, suicide inhibitors function by being cleaving the active site peptide (Fig. 3). However, most serine PIs operate through a tight-binding, reversible mechanism (Vorster et al., 2023). For example, trypsin and chymotrypsin inhibitors have been reported of 4.47 and 3.56 IU/mg, respectively, in raw faba beans (Alonso et al., 2001).

The extraction and analysis of various PI isoforms slight differences in protein length, amino acid sequence, specificity, and structural stability following heat treatment. Protease inhibitors are classified by molecular weight into two major categories: Kunitz-type and Bowman-Birk inhibitors (BBIs). Beyond inhibiting trypsin and chymotrypsin, BBIs also target elastase, cathepsin G, chymase, protein kinase B, and PI3K. Clinical trials and *in vitro* studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of BBIs against tumour cells, highlighting their potential as a therapeutic agent in cancer treatment. Research indicates that BBIs exhibit anti-proliferative and pro-apoptotic effects on various cancer cell lines, including breast, prostate, and colorectal cancers (Gitlin-Domagalska et al., 2020). The protease inhibitory properties contribute to the modulation of cellular signalling pathways associated with tumour progression and metastasis, supporting the ongoing investigation of BBI as a promising bioactive compound in oncology. BBIs are notably stable to heat and gastric juice and are resistant to proteolytic enzymes, including pepsin and pronase (Clemente, 2014). In a pioneering 1973 study, Odani and Ikenaka showed that a soybean BBI treated with cyanogen bromide and pepsin yielded two active fragments, one inhibiting trypsin and the other inhibiting chymotrypsin, thus demonstrating the dual and distinct action of this protease inhibitor (Odani & Ikenaka, 1973). Similar BBIs exist in lima beans, garden beans, azuki beans, mung beans, groundnuts, and chickpeas, as well as in non-legume sources, such as wheat germ and rice. Interestingly, although chickpea BBI treated with cyanogen bromide and pepsin exhibits features comparable to soybean BBI, the proximity of its double-headed trypsin-chymotrypsin inhibitory sites prevents simultaneous inhibition activity in its active form (Clemente, 2014). In dicotyledonous plants, BBI proteins typically have a conserved 'double-headed' structure. In contrast, most monocotyledonous (monocot) plant BBIs lack the conserved cysteine residues required for chymotrypsin inhibition in the second inhibitory loop, suggesting that monocots possess only BBI-trypsin inhibitory activity (Xie et al., 2021). These examples highlight the high complexity of specificity and stability within the same family of inhibitors.

Serpins (SERin Protease INhibitor) are a well-conserved superfamily of proteins widespread throughout all kingdoms of life. They have the demonstrated ability to inhibit both serine and cysteine proteases. The inhibitory function of serpins has been associated with the regulation of endogenous proteinases (e.g., controlling cell death), and defence

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of Bowman-Birk inhibitors of trypsin (left) and chymotrypsin (right). Panel A) shows the free enzymes with key amino acids involved in inhibition, while Panel B) depicts the enzyme-inhibitor complex. The figure was generated using AlphaFold2 protein structure database.

against exogenous proteases (i.e., pest control) (Jamal et al., 2013). LR-Serpins inhibit both serine and cysteine proteases through a unique “suicide-like” substrate inhibitory mechanism, which has been described in the [Supplementary Material 1](#).

Enzyme inhibition tests are used to directly assess active enzyme inhibitors, making protein extraction under physiological conditions essential for accurate evaluation. Techniques such as high-pressure homogenisation or bead milling can enhance extractability from recalcitrant tissues. Furthermore, testing inhibitory activity before and after thermal denaturation (e.g., by autoclaving) helps confirm that the observed inhibition is specifically related to the enzyme inhibitor.

3.2.2. Lectins

Lectins are a family of carbohydrate-binding proteins found ubiquitously in plants, animals, and microorganisms. Their wide-ranging biological functions have been comprehensively reviewed by others (Elumalai & Lakshmi, 2021). In plants, lectins are present in the edible parts like seeds, bark, and leaves, where they serve as defensive tools against insects and pathogens. They also facilitate protein storage, maintain seed dormancy, and contribute to carbohydrate metabolism. (Dias et al., 2015). Some lectins interact with carbohydrates in plant

cells (endogenous targets), while others recognise carbohydrates on exogenous targets like pathogen surface glycans (De Coninck & Van Damme, 2021). The concentration of lectins varies significantly among edible seed. For instance, kidney beans have the highest concentration at up to 10 mg/g, whereas soybeans, faba beans, and lentils contain a lower amount of approximately 1 mg/g. Cereals generally have the lowest levels, around 0.5 mg/g (Pryme & Aarra, 2021). Depending on environmental factors and the plant’s developmental stage, lectins in seeds can constitute up to 40 % of the total seed storage protein (De Coninck & Van Damme, 2021; Levchuk et al., 2013). In animals and bacteria, these proteins take part in various metabolic pathways, including defence mechanisms. Lectins take part in endocytosis, intracellular transportation, apoptosis induction in tumour cells, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection blocking, bacterial adhesion and migration regulation, blood protein level control, and immune system function by recognising pathogen-specific carbohydrates (Dias et al., 2015).

Structurally, lectins are defined as proteins with at least one domain that specifically binds to the sugar portions of glycoconjugates. Their binding specificity varies widely; for instance, some recognise mannose (e.g., fava bean, lentil lectin, concanavalin A from the jack-bean), others bind to galactose (e.g., ricin from castor seed, jacalin

from jackfruit seed, peanut agglutinin) and still others target N-acetylglucosamine moieties (e.g., wheat germ agglutinin) (De Coninck & Van Damme, 2021). Based on their domains, lectins are categorised in merolectins (a single, monovalent carbohydrate-binding domain), hololectins (at least two domains binding the same sugar), chimerolectins (a binding domain paired with an enzymatic domain), and superlectins (binding structurally unrelated sugars) (Elumalai & Lakshmi, 2021).

Based on their carbohydrate-binding specificity and structural characteristics, lectins can be further classified in: L-type (leguminous), C-type (calcium-dependent), P-type (plant), and F-type (fucose-specific), G-type (galactose-binding lectins), among others, each exhibiting unique biological functions and roles in various organisms (Elumalai & Lakshmi, 2021). Due to their biological activity, the presence of active lectins is a critical consideration in food safety. Injection of active lectins can cause gastrointestinal distress, interfere with nutrient absorption, and potentially damage the gut lining. The risk has led to food product recalls in Europe, such as for semi-processed frozen red kidney beans, as documented in the EU's Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) online database (<https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/rasff-window/screen/search>). Consequently, the quantification of active lectins is a crucial step in the safety assessment of alternative food ingredients like legume protein fractions, especially as novel lectin-containing foods are introduced. Lectins are found in many alternative protein sources, from lentils and faba beans (0.1–1 mg/g) to the microalgae *Chlorella* spp., which exhibits low hemagglutination activity (Chen et al., 2022).

To predict the presence of lectins across different protein sources, we utilised computational tools. The UniLectin database (<https://unilectin.unige.ch/>), a repository of curated and predicted lectins, classifies them into domain folds, and families based on sequence similarity (Bonnardel et al., 2019, 2021; Schneider et al., 2024). Using this resource, we generated a heatmap of the lectin-like proteins in legumes and cereals of interest, with *Phaseolus vulgaris* (common bean) as a reference due to its

association with gastroenteritis. This analysis identified rapeseed and chickpea as having the highest number of expressed lectin-like proteins, followed by lentil and fava, with the L-type lectins being the most represented (Supplementary Fig. 1).

Furthermore, we used LectomeXplore to generate a lectin class heatmap for the phyla *Arthropoda* (focusing on *Acheta domesticus*), *Chlorophyta* (focusing on *Chlorella vulgaris*), and *Pseudomonadota* (focusing on microbial biomass like *Xanthobacter*) (Supplementary Fig. 2a). As data for *Acheta domesticus* (October 2024) were unavailable at the time of the analysis, we used the related species *Gryllus bimaculatus* as a proxy (Fig. 4 and Supplementary Fig. 2b). This analysis revealed that *Gryllus bimaculatus* (Fig. 4) has the most complex lectin-like profile, including chitin-binding, rhamnose-binding, and the ERGIC-VIP (Endoplasmic Reticulum-Golgi Intermediate Compartment Vesicular Integral Membrane Protein) L-type lectins, a secretory glycoprotein that serves as a transport receptor.

In *Chlorella vulgaris*, we observed Fucose (F)- and P-type lectin families, along with calnexin-calreticulin-like lectins. For microbial biomass like *Xanthobacter*, only the cyanovirin-like lectin, an 11-kDa protein of cyanobacterial origin with potent virucidal activity, was annotated (Balzarini, 2006; Mitchell et al., 2017; Sharon & Ofek, 2007). These *in silico* findings suggest that the actual protein expression levels in these ingredients and their potential health implications warrant a dedicated risk assessment.

However, accurately quantifying active lectins is challenging. Currently, there are no universal reference methods, except for the hemagglutination assay food pulses (Supplementary Table 3). This assay uses red blood cells and protein extracts in physiological buffers to detect agglutination. A key limit is the need to maintain osmolarity to prevent cell lysis or lectin deactivation. While effective for easily solubilised seed proteins, applying this method to recalcitrant tissues (e.g., leaves) and walled organisms (e.g., microalgae) is problematic.

Fig. 4. Heatmap visualization of lectin expression in the novel food ingredients (*Gryllus bimaculatus*, *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Xanthobacter autotrophicus*), with a minimum similarity score of 0.35 applied to the reference (Bonnardel et al., 2021).

Similarly, fractionation processes leading that result in poor protein solubility can lead to misinterpretation of results. Extraction methods must also preserve protein structure, precluding the use of ultrasound, or certain chaotropic or reducing chemicals. The commonly used buffers may selectively extract certain proteins, leading to inconclusive or false-negative results in the assay. A multi-platform approach could address these limitations and highlight gaps in current knowledge. Finally, a lack of standardised reporting units, with activity expressed as Hemagglutination Units per mg of ingredient, total protein, or extracted protein, adds confusion to the risk assessment process.

3.2.3. Alpha amylase inhibitors

Alpha-amylase inhibitors (α AIs) block starch degradation by endogenous α -amylase during seed dormancy and protect the seed against pests and predators (Neeta & Discov, 2016). This digestive enzyme is also present in the hydrolytic enzyme pool of moulds, insects, and mammals. To date, researchers have established the existence of six types of α AI in the plant domain: the knottin type, γ thionin-like type, CM-proteins type, Kunitz type, legume lectin-like and thaumatin-like type (Peddio et al., 2022). A closer look at these types reveals distinct characteristics. The CM-type α AIs, also referred as “cereal type” α AIs, are small proteins (120–160 AA) soluble in chloroform/methanol. Many CM-type α AIs are abundant in barley seeds at different stages of maturation (Finnie et al., 2002). The Kunitz-type α AIs can inhibit either α -amylase or trypsin, while some variants can inhibit both. The lectin-like α AIs (namely α AI1 and α AI2) are glycoproteins isolated from a variety of kidney beans. Their name arises from their high degree of sequence homology with lectins expressed from the same legumes. These two isoforms can inhibit amylases in different organisms as; for example, α AI1 can inhibit both mammalian and insect amylases. The thaumatin-like AI is a protein with a molecular mass of approximately 22 kDa. These proteins share significant sequence similarity with pathogenesis-related group 5 (PR-5) proteins and with thaumatin, a potent sweet-tasting protein. Among this class, zeamatin, a bifunctional inhibitor found in *Zea mays*, is the best known. It inhibits porcine pancreatic trypsin and the intestinal amylase of various insects. However, despite the high N-terminal sequence similarity, other thaumatin-like proteins, such as those from barley seeds, show no inhibitory activity against trypsin or α -amylases (Franco et al., 2002).

While the knottin-like, the Kunitz, and the thaumatin-like types appear to inhibit amylase only in insects, the other types (γ Thionin-like type, cereal type, and legume lectins-like) can inhibit amylase in both insects and mammals (Svensson et al., 2004). Investigating mammal α AIs is a critical aspect of assessing digestibility and bioavailability of macronutrients, especially in the context of alternative starchy food ingredients from pseudocereals, minor legumes and cereals. For example, the content and activity of α AIs have been reported for various legumes, with faba beans containing 18.90 IU/g (Alonso et al., 2001).

3.2.4. Thiaminases

Thiaminases are enzymes that degrade thiamine (vitamin B1), a crucial nutrient for energy metabolism. These enzymes exist in two forms, Thiaminase I (Thiamine pyridinylase, EC 2.5.1.2, InterPro: IPR030901) and Thiaminase II (Aminopyrimidine aminohydrolase, EC 3.5.99.2, InterPro: IPR027574, IPR004305), and are found in certain raw fish, shellfish, bacteria some plants and seeds. When consumed regularly without proper preparation, they can pose a risk of thiamine deficiency (Bitsch, 2003). Cooking or food processing typically inactivates thiaminases, thereby reducing the risk. The biological function of these enzymes has long been an enigma. Thiaminases break down thiamine by catalysing the base-exchange reaction that substitutes the thiazole moiety with a nucleophile. Thiaminase I, in particular, is associated with thiamine deficiency syndromes in animals. However, recent research has provided new insights. For instance, Sannino et al. (2018) demonstrated that Thiaminase I improved survival in *Burkholderia thailandensis* strains grown in thiamine-depleted media

compared to isogenic strains lacking the enzyme. Their work suggests that Thiamine I aids survival by cleaving thiamine, its phosphorylated forms, and toxic analogues to release precursors for *de novo* thiamine synthesis. This mechanism allows thiamine auxotrophs to grow more effectively on these precursors than on thiamine itself.

The KEGG db includes thiamine metabolism pathways for microbial biomass like *Xanthobacter* (xau00730) and *Chlorella variabilis* (cvr00730). However, in the available genomic sequences for both organisms, thiaminase I and II are either absent or unannotated. Conversely, the UNIPROT database lists four predicted Thiaminase II isoforms for *Chlorella vulgaris*, derived from EMBL/GenBank/DBJ whole-genome shotgun (WGS) data (EMBL: KAI3427436.1). These isoforms (accession numbers A0A9D4TK12, A0A9D4THA1, A0A9D4TGC6, and A0A9D4TWS4) share 20–59 % sequence identity with the Thiaminase II domain. Similarly, for *Xanthobacter*, a protein inferred from homology (EMBL: TLX41961.1) has been identified as a Pyrroloquinoline-quinone synthase (UNIPROT ID: A0A6C1KDR4) containing a Thiaminase II domain (residues 16–225).

3.3. Toxic anti-nutritional factors (t-ANFs)

Certain components of protein sources, as well as compounds generated during processing regimes such as biotransformation, can be toxic when present above normal concentrations. Among these, nucleic acids, including deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and ribonucleic acid (RNA), are essential polymers of nucleotides found within all cells and viruses (Salim et al., 2023). They are particularly abundant in single-cell proteins and fermentation side-streams, such as brewers' spent yeast (Alonso-Riaño et al., 2021), their high concentration is a result of rapid microbiological growth phases. Unlike some anti-nutritional factors, elevated nucleic acid intake does not hinder nutrient absorption. Instead, it can disrupt purine metabolism, potentially leading to hyperuricemia (high uric acid in the blood), kidney stone formation, and gout (Sharif et al., 2021). Single-cell proteins and hydrolysed yeasts can contain 6 %–15 % nucleic acids, with a daily consumption of up to 33 g of yeast considered Generally Recognized As Safe (GRAS) (Podpora et al., 2016).

A review by Ritala et al. (2017) identified nucleic acids as a significant safety concern in SCPs. For example, bacterial SCPs may contain 8–12 % nucleic acids (primarily RNA), while fungi-based SCPs contain slightly lower levels of 7–10 %. To address this, enzymatic strategies have been developed to reduce nucleic acid content. In the manufacturing of Quorn™ mycoproteins from *Fusarium venenatum*, heat-activated endogenous ribonucleases are employed to lower RNA levels, ensuring the product is safe for consumption. It is also worth noting that some mycoproteins may present other metabolic effects; for instance, *in vitro* evidence suggests they can sequester bile salts, potentially affecting lipid absorption (Colosimo et al., 2020).

A separate class of anti-nutritional compounds includes toxic glycosides, which are secondary metabolites that serve as defence mechanisms in organisms. These can be broadly categorised: Cyanogenic glycosides found in over 2500 plant species, these compounds are glycosides of α -hydroxynitriles that release cyanide upon enzymatic hydrolysis (Ritmejeriyte et al., 2022). Amygdalin, first isolated from bitter almond seeds (*Amygdalus communis*) is a well-known example. Some plant species, such as tobacco, contain high levels of alkaloid glycosides like nicotine. These are cyclic organic compounds containing nitrogen, found in sources ranging from microalgae and insects to common foods like lupins, potatoes, tomatoes and eggplants. They are classified by their heterocyclic ring structure and can be anti-nutritional by inhibiting digestion or causing symptoms such as vomiting and diarrhoea (Hill, 2003; Pfister et al., 2001; Wink, 2003). For instance, vicine and convicine are glycoalkaloids faba beans responsible for favism. This is a genetic condition where their consumption by individuals with a glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) enzyme deficiency leads to acute hemolytic anemia, the rapid destruction of red blood cells

(Khazaei et al., 2019).

The public health significance of these toxins is underscored by their frequent detection in the food supply. Over the last decade, alkaloid glycosides, primarily pyrrolizidine and tropane alkaloids, have been responsible for over 270 notifications in RASFF, with herbs and spices being the most commonly affected food categories.

4. Effect of processing on anti-nutritional factors

4.1. Ingredient processing: milling, air classification/dry fractionation, wet extraction

Cereal grains are a key source of carbohydrates and fibre, but they also provide significant protein, with consumption often exceeding that of meat in parts of Africa, Central America, Asia, and Europe. The average phytic acid content in cereal flour ranges from 0.72 to 1.01 g/100 g; oats typically have the highest content and durum wheat the lowest. Interestingly, the phytic acid content in vital wheat gluten increases to 1.9 g/100 g because of the wet extraction process concentrates phytic acid along with the proteins (Hidvegi & Lastity, 2003).

Three distinct forms of protein ingredients exist: wholegrain or protein-enriched flours (15–40 % protein content), protein concentrates (40–85 % protein), and protein isolates (>85 % protein). Dehulling and milling typically produce protein-enriched flours. In contrast, protein concentrates can be produced via dry separation (milling combined with air classification) or wet extraction (alkali extraction followed by acid precipitation).

Dry separation involves dehulling, followed by a series of milling and air classification steps. methods work by exploiting particle size differences; an upward air stream lifts smaller, lighter particles like protein bodies into a fine protein rich fraction, leaving larger, dense starch granules behind as the coarse fraction. Depending on the raw material, this process can achieve protein concentration as high as 60 %. A major advantage of dry separation is that it is a solvent free process that preserves the native properties of proteins. However, a significant challenge is that ANFs are co-enriched with the protein and remain active due to the lack of heating and washing steps. For instance, air classification of faba beans into faba protein concentrate increased the content of vicine and convicine alkaloids contents from 11 to 16 mg/g and from 6 to 9 mg/g, respectively. In the same process, trypsin inhibitor activity (TIA) increased from 2 to 4 TI units/mg, phytic acid content rose from 23 to 32 mg/g, and condensed tannins increased from 2 to 3 mg/100 g (as catechin equivalent/100 g) (Coda et al., 2015).

In contrast, wet-extracted protein isolates, while less sustainable and more costly, typically contain minimal to no active ANFs. The quantity of residual active ANFs depends on factors such as pH, the number of washing steps, and final drying conditions. For example, wet extracted faba beans protein isolates with 90 % protein content are free of vicine and convicine and show a significant reduction in TIA (from 4 to 0.3 TI units/mg protein) compared to a dry-fractionated faba protein concentrate with 64 % protein content (Vogelsang-O'Dwyer et al., 2020). While effective at removing major ANFs, the harsh processing conditions of wet-extraction can compromise protein functionality. Similarly, Albe-Slabi et al. (2020) reported that selective extraction of sunflower albumins at pH 4.1 with 0.25 mol L⁻¹ NaCl achieved over 70 % albumin recovery and reduced phenolic contamination to below 1.6 mg chlorogenic acid per gram of protein, while also lowering phytic acid in the residual meal to less than 4 % dry matter. In rapeseed, Albe-Slabi et al. (2022) demonstrated that extraction at pH 2.0–3.75 with 0.11–0.2 mol L⁻¹ NaCl and moderate temperatures (20–55 °C) yielded more than 55–75 % napin with over 95 % purity while reducing phytic acid in the solid residue to below 4 %. A hybrid two-step process involving dry fractionation followed by wet extraction was found to increase phytic acid by 48 %, TIA by 174 % and total phenolics by 328 % in faba bean protein concentrates relative to the residual coarse starch-rich flour (Dumoulin et al., 2021). According to FAO/WHO reports, the

bioavailability of minerals like iron, calcium, and zinc should be evaluated in relation to their chelation with phytates (PA). Acceptable molar PA-to-mineral ratios are suggested to be < 1 for iron (ideally 0.4), 0.24–0.17 for calcium, and 5–15 for zinc. Wet extraction and spray drying can enhance mineral solubilisation, leading to higher retention of calcium, iron, and zinc in the protein fraction, which has lower phytic acid levels than air-classified fractions (Dumoulin et al., 2021). Future research should focus on mineral and phytic acid solubility and investigate the use of enzymatic or thermal treatments to reduce phytic acid and improve mineral retention.

4.2. Soaking, cooking, autoclaving

Soaking faba beans for 12 h at 30 °C has been shown to reduce phytate content by 33 % and the condensed tannins by 48 %, although this method has little effect on the activity of total phenolics, trypsin inhibitor, α -amylase inhibitor (α -AI) (Avanza et al., 2013). In another study, dehulling slightly increased the α -AI activity (4.99 and 3.71 IU/mg) whereas soaking and germination decreased it significantly 0.05 and 1.68 IU/mg (Alonso et al., 2000). Thermal treatments are also effective; pressure cooking reduces polyphenols, tannins, and phytic acid, with studies showing a 50–65 % reduction in total polyphenols and a 55–71 % reduction in through solubilisation and heat-induced degradation. Due to its heat sensitivity, decreases phytic acid content can be decreased by 55 % through autoclaving, a process that has also been found to increase protein *in vitro* digestibility by up to 12 % (Avanza et al., 2013). Furthermore, using L-cysteine to treat chickpea reduced TIA by 89 % proving more effectively than autoclaving alone without affecting water solubility or absorption. This makes it a promising method for enhancing chickpea protein functionality (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018).

However, ingredient processing technologies and basic food techniques alone (e.g., soaking, cooking, autoclaving, high-pressure cooking) are often insufficient on their own to produce healthy and appealing food products. Additional processing steps are necessary to formulate meat and dairy alternatives that are affordable, nutritionally safe, high in digestible protein, and sensorily pleasing. These steps can be incorporated by products either during ingredient production manufacturing or within the final food design process.

4.3. Germination

Seed germination activates endogenous enzymes such as phytase, amylases, and proteases. This process reduces ANFs like phytates and tannins while enhancing amino acid availability and protein digestibility. Specifically, phytase and other phosphatases break down phytates into beneficial nutrients, including phosphate, inositol, and various micronutrients. Studies have observed significant phytate reductions of approximately 60 % in both chickpeas and pigeon peas (Ohanenye et al., 2022). The germination medium itself also influences phytate breakdown; for example, distilled water causes greater degradation than tap water, likely due to the absence of inhibitory metal-phytate complexes (Sattar et al., 1990). In various lentil varieties, germination of has been shown to reduce phytate content by 40–59 %. Similarly, germination in faba beans reduces the chelating InsP6 form in favour of the less active InsP3 form, thereby enhancing mineral absorption (Raes et al., 2014).

Compared to thermal treatments, germination is generally more effective at lowering phytic acid in legumes, but its effect on other ANFs can be inconsistent across studies. For instance, while TIA in faba beans reportedly decreased by 25 % after three days of germination, some studies have noted an increase after nine days (Muzquiz et al., 2004; Patterson et al., 2017). Germination also reduces total phenolic content and tannins, with its effectiveness varying by legume type, it reduced phenolic content by 21 % in faba bean but by 75 % in peas (Patterson et al., 2017). The pruyrimidine glycosides vicine and convicine

decreased by 30–38 % after three days of germination at 25 °C, while a nine-days germination at 20 °C reduced vicine 86 % and eliminated convicine (Jamalian, 1999). In rapeseed meal, myrosinase catalyses the hydrolysis of glucosinolates (GLs) into glucose and β -aglycone, which subsequently then converts into isothiocyanates (ITCs), oxazolidinethione (OZT), thiocyanates, or nitriles, depending on the conditions. Myrosinase activity and content increase during germination, leading to a GLs reduction of over 80 % within 4 h under controlled conditions (C. Xie et al., 2022). Finally, germination of chickpeas has been shown to reduce trypsin inhibitors by 27–34 %, phytic acid by 26–33 %, tannins by 23–35 %, condensed tannins by 33–36 %, and α -amylase inhibitors by 52–54 % through enzymatic hydrolysis (Roy et al., 2019). It also effectively reduces the active lectin content in white kidney beans and mitigates the effects of other ANFs, such as alkaloids and raffinose family oligosaccharides (Ohanenye et al., 2022).

4.4. Fermentation

Fermented soybean-based products, such as tempeh, soy sauce, and natto, undergo natural or controlled fermentation involving specific microbial strains. Tempeh is produced via solid-state fermentation using *Rhizopus* species, (e.g., *R. oligosporus*), while soy sauce production involves a two-step process: Koji fermentation with *Aspergillus oryzae*, followed by Moromi fermentation with salt-tolerant microbes like *Tetragenococcus halophilus*, and yeasts like *Zygosaccharomyces rouxii*. These processes enzymatically break down ANFs, improving both the digestibility and nutritional quality of soy products. In tempeh, *Rhizopus* enzymes degrade major storage proteins (glycinin and β -conglycinin), trypsin inhibitors and flatulence-causing oligosaccharides (Huang et al., 2019). Similarly, fermentation with *Bacillus subtilis* to produce natto results in a 91.28 % decrease in stachyose and a near-total elimination of raffinose compared to steamed soybeans, making it a highly digestible product (Miao et al., 2024). In addition to targeting carbohydrates, fermentation also reduces other ANFs. In addition to carbohydrates, fermentation also targets other ANFs. Microbial extracellular phytases from *Bacillus*, yeasts, and fungi can lower phytate content by up to 90 %, though the degree of degradation is highly strain-specific, highlighting the importance of careful microbial selection (Huang et al., 2019; Raes et al., 2014).

Furthermore, fermentation catalyses the biotransformation of soybean saponins. Microbial consortia, including *Bacillus subtilis* and *Aspergillus oryzae*, selectively deacetylate group A saponins, key contributors to unpleasant taste, thereby enhancing both palatability and bioactivity (Chen et al., 2023; Xue et al., 2024). The organic acid produced during fermentation also promotes mineral absorption by forming soluble complexes with iron and zinc. This synergistic action makes fermented soy products valuable for the developing functional foods.

In a comparative study, Coda et al. (2015) evaluated spontaneous versus lactic acid bacteria (LAB)-inoculated fermentation for modifying the composition of faba bean flours and their protein and starch components. While the total phenolic and phytic acid content remained stable under both conditions, the targeted use of LAB cultures effectively decreased condensed tannin levels, likely due to the combined action of endogenous enzymes from the faba bean and those produced by the LAB. LAB-driven fermentation demonstrated superior efficacy, leveraging bacterial proteases to achieve an 86 % reduction in TIA. In contrast, spontaneous fermentation paradoxically caused a slight increase. The advantage of LAB was even more pronounced in reducing vicine and convicine, achieving a decrease of over 90 %, compared to the 21–35 % reduction from spontaneous fermentation. Rapeseed meal, a by-product of the rapeseed oil industry, is a rich source of proteins that can be concentrated via dry fractionation (approximately 34 % protein) or wet extraction (approximately 94 % protein). However, its nutritional value is limited by ANFs such as glucosinolates, phenolic compounds, oligosaccharides (like raffinose and stachyose), and phytates, which can negatively affect protein absorption and impart undesirable flavours

(Jia et al., 2021). For instance, a rapeseed protein isolate (RPI) contained 0.02 % phytic acid and condensed tannin 18.7 mg/100 g dry matter, while a dry fractionated rapeseed protein concentrate (RPC) contained 1.26 % phytic acid and 146.0 mg/100 g of tannins. Sourdough fermentation with *Weissella confusa*, which produces dextran, reduced condensed tannins in RPI but increased them in RPC, without significantly altering phytic acid levels. The reduction in RPI likely stemmed from enzyme activation, while the increase in RPC may have resulted from dietary fibre breakdown (Wang et al., 2022).

Biomass fermentation utilises microorganisms like yeasts, bacteria, fungi, and algae as sustainable alternatives. Microalgae such as *Arthrospira* and *Chlorella* show promise for creating nutritious meat analogues, though challenges remain in texture, odour, and large-scale processing remain (Augustin et al., 2024). A common biomass-based protein ingredient is bacterial single-cell protein (SCP), which presents nutritional challenges, particularly its high nucleic acid content (Gundupalli et al., 2024). Advanced processing techniques, including thermal, chemical, and enzymatic degradation, are required to reduce nucleic acid levels by up to 80 %. Additionally, the rigid cell wall structure of certain microbial strains limits nutrient bioavailability, making techniques like sonication, high-pressure homogenisation, and enzymatic cell disruption are essential for improving digestibility of SCP (Aghababaei et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024).

4.5. Enzymatic modification as part of ingredient processing

Enzymatic treatment with phytase effectively reduces phytic acid by breaking down phytate complexes. For instance, one study on native faba bean reported an 80 % reduction in phytic acid after 1 h with 20 U of phytase. A maximum reduction of 89 % (from an initial 9.7 mg/g) was achieved after 4 h, with the effect following an exponential trend, where phytase concentration above 10 U yielded minimal additional benefit (Rosa-Sibakov et al., 2018). In the same study, fermentation with *Lactobacillus plantarum* for 24 h lowered the phytic acid content from 9.7 to 8.8 mg/g. However, this reduction was considered significant, as a similar decrease was caused by the faba bean's endogenous phytases rather than microbial activity.

Consequently, the direct phytase treatment resulted in a much greater increase in protein solubility during gastric digestion compared to *L. plantarum* fermentation. At pH 3, protein solubility in phytase-treated samples reached 74–77 %, compared to just 30 % in native faba beans (Rosa-Sibakov et al., 2018). The necessity of adding phytase for substantial degradation was reinforced by another study, which found that phytase treatment lowered phytic acid in a dry-fractionated RPC from 6 % to 0.5 % (Silventoinen et al., 2022).

4.6. Extrusion processing

High-moisture extrusion (HME) is a technology used to produce meat analogue, employing twin-screw extruders at high temperatures (140–180 °C) and water levels (40–70 %). The process incorporates a long cooling die that aligns the protein into a fibrous, meat-like structure (Pöri et al., 2023). Extrusion processing is highly effective at reducing ANFs through high temperature and high shear processing. For example, extrusion of faba bean flour, has been shown to reduce phytate (27 %), tannins (54 %), phenolics (29 %), protease inhibitors (99 %), α -amylase inhibitors (53–100 %), and hemagglutinating activity (99.5 %). Similarly, low-moisture extrusion of pea flour (148 °C, 25 % moisture, 100 rpm) reduced trypsin inhibitors by 95 %, chymotrypsin inhibitors by 65 %, and condensed tannins by 83.6 % (Alonso et al., 2001). Other studies summarised by Nikmaram et al. (2017) show that extruding lentil flour at 180 °C reduced phytic acid and condensed tannins by 99 % and polyphenols by up to 65 %, while in oat bran, it reduced phytate, polyphenols, oxalates, and trypsin inhibitors by 54.5 %, 73.4 %, 36.8 %, and 72.4 %, respectively. Thermal degradation during extrusion appears to reduce phytic acid by forming insoluble complexes, with reductions

influenced by process parameters such as temperature, screw speed, and feed moisture content. The optimal conditions for reducing phytates and polyphenols were found to be 20 % feed moisture and temperatures between 140 °C and 160 °C (Nikmaram et al., 2017).

Despite these findings, the effect of extrusion on phytic acid is debated in the literature. While thermal degradation is reported to begin at 150 °C (Daneluti & Matos, 2013). Studies on hemp protein and pinto bean fractions showed no significant changes in phytic acid concentration after extrusion (Nasrollahzadeh et al., 2022; Simons et al., 2017).

This discrepancy may stem from different analytical methods; research showing a reduction used the IEC method, while those reporting no effect frequently used a phytase colorimetric method (McKie & McCleary, 2016). Given the critical role of phytic acid in mineral bioavailability, refining analytical approaches is critical to accurately determine the impact of extrusion and ensure a nutritionally sound dietary transition.

A powerful strategy for ANF reduction involves combining bio-processing with thermal processing. For example, phenolic compounds are a major ANF in oil-press meals like sunflower protein concentrates (SPC). In one study, the SPC was first fermentation with *Lactobacillus helveticus*, reducing its chlorogenic acid (CGA) content from 34 mg/g to 22 mg/g. A subsequent pH shifts further lowered the CGA content to 19 mg/g. Finally, the pre-treated SPC was mixed with pea protein and subjected to HME, which reduced the final CGA content in the extrudates to just 7 mg/g (Pöri et al., 2023). This demonstrates that combining bio-processing (e.g., fermentation) and physical processing (e.g., extrusion) can act orthogonally to modulate ANFs, offering a more effective and comprehensive reduction strategy.

4.7. Emerging processing technologies

Emerging non-thermal and thermal technologies show greater potential for reducing ANFs in legume seeds. Technologies such as high-pressure processing (HPP), ultrasound, irradiation, pulsed electric fields (PEF), and microwave heating have been highlighted for their effectiveness in enhancing nutritional quality of legumes (Ohanenye et al. (2022)).

High Pressure Processing (HPP), also known as high hydrostatic pressure, is a non-thermal technology that applies extreme pressures to break down complex protein structures and deactivate ANFs. For example, HPP treatment of pea reduced phytic acid content by 36 % and total phenolic content by 30 %, while eliminating trypsin inhibitor activity (Linsberger-Martin et al., 2013). HPP reduced trypsin inhibitors in chickpeas by 60 % and decreased lectin activity by 50 %. These reductions contributed to a significant improvement in protein digestibility. For instance, HPP at 600 MPa increased the *in vitro* protein digestibility (IVPD) of white beans and split peas by 8.7 % and 4.3 %, respectively (Linsberger-Martin et al., 2013). A key advantage of HPP is its ability to preserve heat-sensitive nutrients while targeting ANFs. However, its effectiveness can be context dependent (Sanaei Nasab et al., 2024). While processing can degrade heat-sensitive lectins like favin in faba beans, other heat stable lectins may remain (Sharan et al., 2021). Furthermore, a combination of traditional methods like soaking and cooking found to be more effective than HPP alone in reducing total phenolic acid (71 % reduction), and trypsin inhibitors (100 % reduction) in some applications (Linsberger-Martin et al., 2013).

Ultrasound uses high-frequency sound waves to induce cavitation in the food matrix, which disrupts ANFs. When applied during the soaking of lentils, chickpeas, peas, and soybeans, ultrasound inactivated trypsin inhibitors and saponins, resulting in a 2–4 % increase in *in vitro* protein digestibility (IVPD) by improving the accessibility of digestive enzymes (Han et al., 2007). In mung beans, ultrasound treatment reduced phytic acid and tannin levels by 25 % and 15–20 %, respectively (Rana & Dahiya, 2021).

Irradiation employs gamma rays or electron beams to break the molecular bonds in ANFs. Doses up to 30 kGy have been shown to

eliminate the phytic acid in legumes such as pigeon peas and velvet beans, significantly boosting their digestibility (Bhat et al., 2007).

Cold plasma technology generates reactive species that interact with and disrupt the molecular structure of ANFs, particularly tannins, saponins and lectins. In lentils, cold plasma treatment reduced tannin content by 35 %, which enhanced protein digestibility (Sanaei Nasab et al., 2024). This technology has also been shown to reduce lectin activity by 20–30 %, further improving the safety and digestibility of legumes (Avilés-Gaxiola et al., 2018).

Other promising technologies include dielectric-barrier discharge (DBD) plasma, which has shown potential in reducing soybean trypsin inhibitors (Li et al., 2017) and microwave heating. The latter improved IVPD in pigeon peas from 54.4 % to 71.6 % by reducing tannins, phytic acid, and trypsin inhibitors, and by inducing structural modifications that made the proteins more accessible (Ozolina et al., 2023). Collectively, these emerging technologies these emerging technologies are important tools for enhancing legume protein bioavailability by degrading ANFs.

5. Potential beneficial effects of anti-nutritional factors

While typically viewed as detrimental, ANFs can also exert beneficial effect on human health when consumed at low concentrations. This dual role challenges the conventional perspective of ANFs as solely harmful compounds, with a growing body of research supporting their potential as bioactive molecules. Indeed, certain ANFs, such as polyphenols and α -amylase inhibitors, are utilised in the management of type-2 diabetes. They function by slowing down the glucose absorption, which is achieved by impairing starch digestion in the small intestine (Salim et al., 2023). By inhibiting the α -amylase, these inhibitors allow undigested starch to reach the colon, where it is fermented by the gut microbiota (Kashtoh & Baek, 2023).

The synergistic effects of polyphenols, undigested macromolecules, and dietary fibres in reducing the risk of chronic diseases are well-established. These benefits stem from their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and their interaction with gut bacteria, which ferment these compounds into bioactive molecules. For instance, the gut microbiota ferments fibres to produce short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), including acetate, propionate, and butyrate. These SCFAs not only serve as an energy source for colon cells but also play crucial roles in improving gut barrier integrity, regulating glucose and lipid metabolism, modulating the immune system, and reducing inflammation (A. P. Kaur et al., 2021; Nogal et al., 2021). Butyrate, in particular, supports the intestinal lining by promoting cell proliferation and differentiation, thereby strengthening the gut barrier.

The production of SCFAs through fibre fermentation also influences appetite regulation by promoting the release of satiety signalling hormones, which helps control food intake and support weight management. Furthermore, a substantial body of evidence indicates that SCFAs are pivotal in microbiota-gut-brain communication, regulating neuro-immunoendocrine functions, with both short- and long-term effects on brain health (Loh et al., 2024). SCFAs also modulate key cellular processes, like phagocytosis and apoptosis, influencing overall health and resistance to infection (Ney et al., 2023). In addition, gut microbiota dysbiosis is a leading factor in food allergies (FA), and SCFAs act as key regulators in mitigating these conditions (Chen et al., 2023).

Specific np-ANFs have demonstrated positive effects on gut health. Phytic acid may influence liver fat levels and gut microbiota, potentially decreasing insulin resistance (Y. Li et al., 2024). Raffinose family oligosaccharides (RFOs) show prebiotic potential by promoting the growth of beneficial bacteria, such as *Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacillus* spp. which in turn produces SCFAs that inhibit harmful microbes (Kanwal et al., 2023).

Saponins have been shown to enhance intestinal barrier function, reduce inflammation, and exert protective effects on the gut–liver axis (Cao et al., 2024; Dong et al., 2019). Indeed, dietary saponins promising

anti-diabetic capabilities by regulating signalling pathways across the liver, pancreas, gut, and skeletal muscle (Zhou & Xu, 2023).

Similarly, some proteinaceous ANFs (p-ANFs) show beneficial potential. While protease inhibitors interfere with protein digestion, studies indicate they can also modulate the gut microbiota and reduce inflammation, offering therapeutic potential for conditions like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) by helping restore balance in the gut environment (Vergnolle, 2016).

Other ANFs, such as lectins, have complex roles; they can affect the turnover of gut epithelial cells, stimulate shifts in the bacterial flora, and modulate the immune state of the digestive tract's immune system. This highlights the intricate, dose-dependent nature of ANFs, where the line between beneficial and detrimental effects requires further investigation.

6. Conclusions and perspectives

This review highlights the complex role of anti-nutritional factors (ANFs) in the shift towards sustainable, protein-rich ingredients. As the food industry embraced novel sources like insects, algae and microbial biomasses, the primary challenge is to ensuring their nutritional safety and quality. A crucial finding is that mitigating ANFs effectively requires a multi-target processing approach, as a single technique is often insufficient. Combining technologies, such as bio-processing with thermal treatment, is a highly effective strategy. For instance, a sequence of fermentation, pH adjustment, and extrusion can significantly reduce chlorogenic acid in sunflower protein concentrate; while combining traditional soaking and cooking can eliminate trypsin inhibitor activity in peas. However, the efficacy of these methods is difficult to validate due to significant limitations in current analytical techniques for assessing "active ANFs", which can lead to data misinterpretation. This underscores a critical need for new or adapted methodologies, especially for novel food matrices. The conclusions, identified gaps, and key areas for future investigation are summarised in Table 2 and outlined below.

While ANFs have historically been viewed as detrimental to nutrient bioavailability and digestion, emerging research suggests a more nuanced role. Some ANFs, such as glucosinolates, may offer potential health benefits. Additionally, the interaction between ANFs and gut microbiota presents a promising avenue for future research, with implications for functional food development, starting from these alternative ingredients.

To ensure consumer trust and safety, a collaborative effort among researchers, food business operators, and policymakers is required. Integrating innovative processing, robust analytics, and a modern understanding of ANF bioactivity are essential to create the clear labelling and regulatory frameworks needed to unlock the full potential of sustainable food systems.

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Table 2

Future research directions for anti-nutritional factors (ANFs) in novel food ingredients. The table outlines current knowledge, existing knowledge gaps, and proposed future strategies to enhance ANF identification, detection methodologies, food processing techniques, health impact assessments, and the role of artificial intelligence in ANF research.

Key Area	Current knowledge	Knowledge Gaps	Future directions
<i>Identification of ANFs in Novel Ingredients</i>	Plant-derived ANFs have a strong track record.	Limited knowledge on occurrence, active levels, and metabolic pathways of ANFs in novel ingredients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Phylogenetic analysis to predict ANF presence. - Improved annotation of genomic, metabolomic, and proteomic databases. - Proteomics/metabolomics to identify ANF expression using LC-MS or NMR. - Develop and validate multi-analytical approaches for active ANF quantification in novel ingredients.
<i>Methodologies for ANF Detection</i>	Validated methods exist for traditional food ingredients/products.	Challenges in extracting ANFs from novel ingredients because of solubility loss and cell wall interference.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In vitro and in vivo digestibility studies to validate processing protocols for ANF reduction.
<i>Effect of Food Processing Technologies</i>	Bio-based and innovative technologies can deactivate ANFs, improving ingredient suitability.	Insufficient understanding of how processing affects ANFs in novel ingredients.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long-term human studies on ANF effects. - Cell-based assays to assess biological activity. - Exploring beneficial ANF roles for food and pharmaceutical applications.
<i>Health effects of ANFs</i>	ANFs can reduce bioavailability and accessibility of nutrients but may offer benefits for glucose/lipid metabolism and gut microbiome health.	Limited understanding of long-term health effects and ANF interactions with other dietary components.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-driven modeling for ANF affects nutrient absorption and health. - AI optimization of food processing techniques. - Development of AI-based personalized dietary recommendations.
<i>Artificial Intelligence (AI) in ANF Research</i>	AI can analyze large datasets and optimize processing.	Application of AI in ANF prediction, interaction studies, and personalized nutrition remains under-explored.	

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgments

The present study received co-funding from the EU Horizon Europe research and innovation program [grant agreement No 101059632].

Nomenclature

AI	Amylase Inhibitor
ANF	Anti-nutritional factor
BBI	Bowman-Birk inhibitor
CGA	Chlorogenic acid
CM-type	Cereal-type
CVD	Cardio-Vascular-Disease
DE	Dimensional Electrophoresis
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
FA	Food Allergy
FAO/WHO	Food and Agriculture Organization/World Health Organization
FBO	Food Business Operator
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FSA	Food Standard Agency
FSANZ	Food Standards Australia New Zealand
G6PD	Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase
GRAS	Generally Recognized As Safe
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HME	High-Moisture Extrusion
HPP	High-Pressure Processing
IBD	Inflammatory Bowel Disease
InsP6	Myoinositol 6-hexakis dihydrogen phosphate
IU	Inhibitory unit
IVPD	In vitro Protein Digestibility
LAB	Lactic Acid Bacteria
Leu	Leucine
LR-Serpine	Leucine-Arginine serpin
L-type	Legume-type
MPa	Megapascal
MW	Molecular weight
np-ANF	Non-proteinaceous anti-nutritional factor
PA	Phytic acid
p-ANF	Proteinaceous anti-nutritional factor
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PEF	Pulsed Electric Field
PI	Protease inhibitor
PI3K	Phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase
PR	Pathogenesis-related
PRP	Proline-Rich Protein
RASFF	Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed
RCL	Reactive Centre Loop
RFO	Raffinose family oligosaccharide
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RPC	Rapeseed Protein Concentrate
RPI	Rapeseed Protein Isolate
Rpm	Revolution per minute
SBS	Substrate-Binding Site
SCFAs	Short-Chain Fatty Acids
SCP	Single Cell Protein
Ser	Serine
SPC	Sunflower Protein Concentrate
t-ANF	Toxic anti-nutritional factor
TI	Trypsin Inhibitor
TIA	Trypsin Inhibitor Activity
Tyr	Tyrosine
Xaa	Small amino acid residue

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2025.105365>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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